

Impacts of China's Higher Education Reforms: Focus on the C9 League and Other Peer Institutions

Spencer Amoo-Dotse^{1*}

¹ College of Education, Master of Education Management, Huzhou University, China

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*Corresponding Author:
Spencer Amoo-Dotse,

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the elitist policies adopted and implemented by the Chinese government in the early 1990s, which gave a re-birth to higher education modernization in China. The article also recounts the policy frameworks adopted in the years passed by the Chinese government in the higher education sub-sector. Events which preceded formulation of policies and frameworks for the drafting and smooth implementation of the project 211 and the project 985, which later amalgamated into the C9 league of universities, also referred to as China's "Ivy League", was carefully looked at. The ARWU global university rankings was utilized as a benchmark for this study. Data from the ARWU from the year 2016 to 2020 was collected and studied for the purposes of this study. Performance of the Chinese universities, that form the C9 league was looked at in terms of worldwide rankings from 2016 to 2020 fundamentally to check their performance in the past five years which revealed the positive exploits of the "C9 League" of Chinese universities. Furthermore, the C9 League was studied alongside other Chinese universities which are not part of the "top-tier" class but have made tremendous gains on the ARWU global ranking scale. Discovery was made which points to the fact that there are universities in China that are not so popular but have made significant gains on the ARWU scale. These schools are found to be the "unsung heroes" making waves locally but not on the international stage. This makes it paramount for stakeholders in the higher education sub-sector in China to pay special attention to. Also analyzing the data accentuated the fact that, policies implement with the aim of modernizing higher education, have yielded positive results. The positions of these institutions on the international scale were looked at in relation to the other schools that are in the "C9 league". Also, it was discovered that in the last three years (2018 - 2020), the C9 league of institutions have made steady progress on the global ranking scale which is gradually making Chinese higher education world class and a worth explorable topic.

Keywords: CHINA, HIGHER EDUCATION, GLOBAL UNIVERSITY RANKINGS, PROJECT 211, PROJECT 985, C9 LEAGUE.

Introduction

Higher education management in China is carried out at two levels; these levels are the central and provincial

governments. The term “regular” is utilized to draw the distinction between formal and non-formal institutions of higher learning. At the level of central government, 73 institutions of higher instruction are administered by the ministry of education (MOE) and 38 by other services. At the common level, 1,538 institutions are administered by the provincial governments as well as governments of independent districts or regions. In expansion, there are 656 non-state run (private) universities (Chinese Service of Instruction, 2010b). The ministry of education (MOE) as the essential useful division of the State Committee in higher education is responsible for the arrangement of improved national teaching and learning. In each university, there's a university Party Committee. The highest position within the university's Party Committee is the Party Committee Secretary (ordinarily interpreted into english as chancellor), who leads a Standing Party Committee. Han (1993) stated that the Party committee's political supervision is executed within the university through different party branches and sub-branches at all levels of the university. For all intents and purposes for every scholastic administrative head, there's a parallel party secretary. According to (Tsang, 2000), in the year 1990, the Chinese government unveiled policies tailored towards the advancement of science and technology education at the higher education level, with budgetary support from the government. The dedication and vision of the general secretary of the Chinese Communist Party at the time, Jiang Zemin, enabled the government to propose and implement a high profile Project 211 in a five-year (1996-2000) plan. The project targeted investment at the top tiers of the higher education sector, with explicit goals of meeting a top-notch standard in teaching and research (Ngok & Guo, 2008). Hundred institutions of higher learning were selected for the project with a total endowment of around US\$2.2 billion, where the universities selected in this project became key institutions for the Chinese domestic sector (L. Li, 2004). Due to the positive exploits of Project 211, while delivering a speech at Peking University's centennial anniversary in 1998, Jiang Zemin declared that China should have many globally recognized institutions, saying, “China must have a number of first-class universities of international standard and appeal”, which gave rise to the commissioning of the “project 985”. In 1999, the government of China injected a major investment into its higher education sector, focusing on higher education. This project was known as the “project 985”. Funding was targeted at a number of selected elite institutions. The project's objectives was as it were, to bring to the fore, globally renowned institutions of international acclaim. The total investment by the government was about 27 billion Chinese yuan, which was allocated to thirty- four universities. Out of the thirty-four schools, nine received a chunk of the endowment which was about forty-two percent of the total endowment (Yue & Zhu, 2009). These nine universities have since become part of what is known today as the “China 9 University League” (C9 League), which has been dubbed the “Ivy League” of China (Chinese Ministry of Education, 2014; Fang et al., 2013). The C9 league of Chinese universities comprises China's most comprehensive leading public research universities. Its members (in no particular order) are Fudan University, Harbin Institute of Technology, Nanjing University, Peking University, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, Tsinghua University, University of Science and Technology of China, Xi'an Jiaotong University, and Zhejiang University. C9 Association of universities are apportioned extraordinary assets, and have uncommon

courses of action for mutually sharing assets. The alumni of these universities have been granted one of China's highest scholarly honors like the “Thousand Talents Plan Professorship” and the “Changjiang (Yangtze River) Professorship” and some also have been regularly granted both of these honors. C9 Association schools get considerable subsidizing from both national and local governments for the purposes of constructing new research centers, improving already existing facilities, hold universal conferences, pull in world-renowned personnel in academia and renowned researchers, as well as offering assistance to the Chinese labour market. This paper goes on to study the impact of the reforms of the Chinese higher education system, while focusing on the topmost rated institutions in the country known as the C9 league of universities and other top performing local universities in China, that are not officially listed among the C9 league. Their performance on the global scale based on renowned world university rankings will also be looked at. World University rankings are a means of evaluating the growth of institutions in terms of research, funding, students achievement, etc.

1. Elite Policies for Chinese higher education

The higher education framework of the People’s Republic of China was built up within the 1950s. The construction of the communist higher education framework in that period was completely based on the Soviet design of an exceedingly centralized and arranged model. Among other things, mergers were utilized as an imperative approach instrument to rebuild the higher education framework. The accentuation of that merger was to regroup and realign institutions of higher instruction in a manner that will decrease needless duplication. According to Zhou (2000), in line with the newly introduced prerequisites emerging from social change and the move towards a market-oriented economy, the government introduced a modern circular of changes to rebuild higher education. The rebuilding followed the rules of joint development, exchange of purview, cooperation, and merger.

In 1998, a previous Vice Premier of China Li Lanqing reformulated the standards of restructuring higher education in eight Chinese characters, notably “gongjian” (joint purview), “tiaozheng” (alteration or exchange of purview), “hezuo” (participation) and “hebing” (merger), which was only a rhetorical change. All of the above methodologies have generally fortified the position of higher education institutions in regional growth by preparing the eagerness of authorities in local governments. In spite of the fact that these jurisdictional changes are not specifically connected to inter-institutional participation, numerous institutions of higher learning concerned have been included in hierarchical unions and mergers afterwards.

“Transfer of jurisdiction” can be caught on as a by-product of the government’s education administrative reform. In this reform, most government ministries are not permitted to run higher education institutions, and consequently, the institutions of higher education initially associated with these government ministries have either been decentralized to local governments at the provincial level or given to China’s ministry of education. “Joint jurisdiction” implies that the central government divisions and nearby specialists ought to cooperatively regulate teaching and learning in institutions of higher education in spite of the fact that one

party ordinarily takes on more responsibilities than the other depending on a two-sided agreement.

A case in point was when the Guangdong provincial government and the Chinese ministry of education agreed to co-administer the Zhongshan University and Huanan University of Science and Technology. Both of the above procedures have to a great extent strengthened the role of higher education institutions by making local authorities more proactive. Though these jurisdictional changes are not directly linked to inter-institutional cooperation, many of the higher education institutions concerned have been involved in alliances and mergers later on. According to F. Zhao (1998), the essential reasons for utilizing mergers amid the introductory changes included figuring out economies of scale, bringing down costs, accomplishing more noteworthy effectiveness, and progressing scholastic quality in higher education. The conviction was that mergers might accomplish cost-effectiveness and increase the effective utilization of educational assets by expanding student-teacher proportions, decreasing the backlog of staff population, and enabling the sharing of facilities. Hao et al (2000), accentuated the fact that higher education enrollment in China increased in China between the years 1977 and 1985. The number of institutions expanded from 404 to 1,016, and the number of enlisted students expanded from 625,319 to 1,703,115. Despite the rapid growth, the average enrolment number per institution remained less than 2,000, and more than a third of the institutions had a student enrolment of less than 1,000 (Min, 1994). Min's 1994 discovery about the disparities in the growth rate and the average enrolment per institution, ignited a hypothetical conversation about the best way to move forward with the higher education instruction framework. Min (1990) recognized two improvement models, specifically an outside extension (*waiyan*) and an inside upgrade (*neihan*) format. In order to begin with the implementation, quality higher education was to be accomplished basically by building up new institutions. This blueprint reflected the improvement of higher instruction within the 1980s. Concurring to the current blueprint, the second model will improve higher education by utilizing inner human resources inside existing higher educational facilities while expanding their inner proficiency. The second model connects significance to economies of scale and cost-effectiveness. H. Wang (2000) stated that, Min's recommendation drew extraordinary consideration from two ministries of state, notably the ministries of finance and education since the idea of inner advancement appeared to have the potential to fathom the situations standing up to the on-going changes, especially the pressure between higher education development and monetary constraints. Subsequently, the administrative changes on higher education within the 1990s, adopted the internal advancement model. Mergers have also been considered as an imperative means in actualizing important legislative approaches, such as "Project 211", concerning building first-class universities, "enrolment expansion" and "government reforms" (Wan, 2003).

1.1 Project 211

According to Tsang (2000), within the early 1990s, the Communist Party of China (CCP) began to divulge approaches targeted at improving science and innovation through the quality advancement of the higher instruction framework with enormous central government subsidizing infusion. One vital angle of Chinese

higher education reforms has been to endeavor to extend China's competitiveness within world. In any case, the top Chinese universities at the time were not competitive and attractive based on worldwide benchmarks. To make strides with regards to the distinction and quality of Chinese higher instruction, the Chinese government progressively propelled "Project 211" in 1995. The motive was to strengthen almost 100 higher educational institutions and a number of key disciplinary zones in terms of educating, research and organization as national needs for the 21st century. The figures of 21 and 1 inside "211" are from the shortened form of the 21st century and around 100 institutions of higher learning respectively. The venture has been actualized since 1995. In expansion, these schools are expected to train, prepare and produce high-level experts and also understanding major issues confronting the country's financial and social advancement. This project focused on investment at the highest levels of the higher education, with unequivocal objectives of building a "world standard" in education and research. According to L. Wang (2008), the selection criteria for the Project 211 schools combines viewpoints of open competition and political consultation. Within the open selection process, a number of candidate institutions which meet the essential criteria set by the Chinese government are surveyed by a group of experts, which separates those not qualified. L. Li (2004) stated that there were 100 institutions of higher education chosen for the pool financing with an endowment of around US\$2.2 billion from 1996 to 2000. Also, an attempt was made to strike a balance between the geographical location of these universities, with regards to their selection. To keep the balance between the eastern and western districts and advance the role of key universities in regional improvement, the chosen project 211 institutions are fundamentally distributed all over the country. For this reason, basically utilizing the list of the project 211 institution to legitimize the quality of Chinese higher education isn't exceptionally precise. A few universities not included within the project list may be more grounded in terms of research and teaching than a few of those (regularly within the west) in the project 211 list. The above observation made it necessary to devise another means of developing and harnessing a group of top-notch universities in China, which made way for the introduction of the "project 985". In the following year, the government officially unveiled a project to inject a major investment into its higher education sub-sector known as the "985 Project" or the "Project 985".

1.2 Project 985

"Project 985" is a national venture for establishing world-class universities within the 21st century, after Jiang Zeming's discourse on May 4, 1998 that "China must have a number of top-notch universities of universal repute". Diverse to the Project 211, the determination of Project 985 institutions of higher learning isn't based on concrete prerequisites and determination criteria. Rather, the institutions within the venture result from conciliation between the education ministry of China and individual universities. Sometimes provincial governments are included within the deliberations or talks that led to the establishment of the "Project 985" group of universities. At the preliminary stages, only two institutions of higher learning namely, Tsinghua University and Peking University were accorded the "Project 985" status. It was announced by the education

ministry of china in 1998 that the two universities, would each get 1.8 billion RMB funding which will be availed within three years (1999-2001) from the central government as extraordinary improvement reserves in expansion to normal government budgetary assignment. According to L. Wang (2008), from 1999-2003, 33 extra universities were recorded as Project 985 institutions through a mode of co-financing between the central government and provincial governments and finally the number of Project 985 schools was expanded to 39. Among these institutions, 11 universities were apportioned special reserves of 600 million RMB or more from the central government and the others get 100-400 million RMB. Yue & Zhu (2009) however accentuated that, the Chinese government's venture totaled almost 27 billion RMB and went to only 34 universities (afterward extended to 39), whereas as it were, nine (9) of the institutions got almost 42% of all the endowment from the central government. These nine universities, according to Fang., et al (2013), have been named "China 9 University League" (C9 League), which others refer to as the "Ivy League" universities of the People's Republic of China.

3.0 The "C9 League" of China

The "C9 League" Universities of China, in no particular order comprises Fudan University, Harbin Institute of Technology, Nanjing University, Peking University, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, Tsinghua University, University of Science and Technology of China, Xi'an Jiaotong University, and Zhejiang University. In October 2008, Zhejiang University (ZJU) facilitated the group's yearly symposium and the joint presidents' assembly in Hangzhou, where different government authorities partook. A few moments later, the presidents re-emerged at a reception where they received the special approval of the Chinese government on the establishment of the C9 league of elite Chinese Universities. They also discussed and agreed to the 'group constitution' drafted by Zhejiang University (ZJU). The group named itself in English as 'Consortium of China Nine Research Universities' or 'C9'. After this joint occasion, the formal document gazetting the group was finalized by the nine presidents. A duplicate was moreover sent to the Chinese ministry of education. The primary self-initiated top-notch university coalition in China was authoritatively built up discreetly. The nine presidents had unanimously concurred to keep a low profile, this notable advancement without drawing too much awareness. They needed to move slowly and dodge residential pressure. They saw their arrangement advancing over a long time towards a more unequivocal organization. With regards to branding, the nine universities would investigate the choices to form an official C9 website, curate a C9 logo, and build up an "IT" platform for mass communications and resource sharing, as well as frame a C9 brand by advancing joint scholarly and social activities, research and community engagement. Zhao (2009), stated that, in 2009, Xian Jiao Tong University became the host of the annual symposium of the C9 presidents' assembly during which Zhao Xingping, who was the immediate past education minister at the time, was invited with other global experts to deliver a speech which focused on the benefits of forming university alliances or partnerships. The C9 Association amalgamation isn't a new re-modelling in higher education concocted by the Chinese, as other similar systems, exist in countries such as the United Kingdom, Australia,

United States of America and Canada (Boli, Ramirez, & Meyer, 1985).

4.0 Global University Rankings

Since 1983, notable organizations in America have been publishing “America’s Best Colleges” which uncovers the evaluation of American Universities in terms of performance. This worldwide phenomenon activated the commencement of ranking systems’ advancement and their multiplication all around the world (Lukman, Kranjnc & Glavic, 2010). According to the European University Association, universal rankings can be classified within the way of institutional association tables speaking to a single amassed score of universities rankings exclusively centered on research, depending on a set of indicators (Jarocka, 2012). University ranking frameworks are valuable apparatuses for prospective students and their families since they give data that helps in evaluating universities comparatively and making choices (Altbach, 2012). Nazarko et al. (2009) states that the frameworks for ranking are strong components for partners within academia with information transparency.

There's significant criticism of university rankings since the claim that they accurately capture higher education brilliance is regularly seen as exaggerated, as the commensurate estimation in ranking tables is regularly narrow or indeed deluding. For instance, Marginson (2014) calls the weighting of measures, such as the sum of articles published by the respective schools in the field of Nature and Science, totally subjective. Besides, the ordinal positioning of each institution, like with the top 100 within the Academic Ranking of World Universities (ARWU), expands the actual difference between teaching and research methods, meaning that the contrast between the rank of 100 as compared with the rank of 25 is nearly insignificant or at slightest not as sharp as the rankings depict (Marginson, 2014). The impacts from rankings moreover reach the most elevated levels of government. Globally, countries around the world have endeavored to boost their higher learning institutions from high-level investment ventures, such as the “Brain Korea 21” project in Korea, comparable to China’s 985 and 211 projects (Shin & Kehm, 2012). Indeed, the World Bank cites the rankings as making a difference in order to devise measures of developing world class universities (Salmi, 2009). Notable among the rankings of the world, are the Times Higher Education (THE) ranking and the Academic Ranking of world Universities (ARWU).

4.1 The Academic Ranking of World Universities (ARWU)

The Academic Ranking of World Universities (ARWU), was first published in 2003 by the Center for World-Class Universities (CWCU), Graduate School of Education of Shanghai Jiao Tong University. Since 2009 the ARWU has been published and copyrighted by Shanghai Ranking Consultancy, which is a completely autonomous association and not legitimately subordinated to any universities or government agencies. ARWU is mainly a research-focused ranking scheme, that ranks universities strictly by their performance in the field of research. Academic Ranking of World Universities (ARWU) is known as one of the foremost well-known universal ranking systems which positions universities all over the world based on research performance.

These universities have their graduated class and staff winning Nobel Prizes and awards in their fields of research and are profoundly cited specialists in 21 wide subject categories with articles written across the broad spectrum of Nature and Science and recorded in SCIE and/or SSCI and scholastic research fields (Liu & Cheng, 2005).

The key 6 performance indicators of the ARWU are,

- ✓ The number of graduated class and staff winning Nobel Prizes and Medals in their respective areas of academic specialization.
- ✓ Number of highly cited researchers chosen by Thomson Reuters.
- ✓ Number of articles published in diaries of Nature and Science.
- ✓ Number of articles indexed in Science Citation Index.
- ✓ Number of articles indexed in Social Sciences Citation Index.
- ✓ Per ca pita performance of the university.

4.1.3 Chinese Universities on global rankings

There are other exceedingly cited university rankings other than ARWU, particularly QS and THE rankings. In this paper, focus will be on the ARWU for a few reasons. To begin with, as mentioned earlier, the Shanghai ranking scheme is the longest persistent worldwide university ranking scheme. Stakeholders at Shanghai Jiao Tong University built up the ARWU with the express objective to “assess the gap between Chinese colleges and world-class universities” (Liu & Cheng, 2005). The institution’s objective, in this manner, is in tandem with the elite-policy yearnings of the Chinese government. Finally, the ARWU’s focus will be mainly research. Marginson (2014) claims that its focus on research gives a few objectivity and straightforwardness, particularly compared with other ranking schemes like the QS and THE, which both utilize subjective recognition scores. At this part of the study, focus will be on Chinese universities and how they are performing on the global ranking scale with regards to the ARWU rankings. The focal point for the data will be on rankings of the ARWU from the year 2016-2020. The ARWU rankings will be looked at critically to evaluate the advancement of Chinese universities on the global scale based on the key indicators of its ranking system. The rankings for the past five years will be considered due to fact that, China has made lots of progress globally, on all fronts which can be attributed to the advancement of its human resource base in research, technology, innovation. China’s influence on the global stage in all spheres of policy making has been impressive.

4.1.3 Performance of Chinese universities on the world stage using the university rankings (focus on the C9 league and other top performers)

The ARWU rankings will be the focus of study. The rankings of Chinese universities will be looked at on the

global rankings, using the ARWU scheme as the baseline or the benchmark for the investigation. As it was stated earlier in the previous session of this paper, the ARWU global rankings is a system that is used to measure the performance of Chinese universities on the global scale specifically. The impact of the reforms that were carried out by the Chinese government in the years past which were sequentially listed will be looked at using the ARWU world rankings as a baseline for the impact assessment. The ARWU data was looked at from the year 2016 to 2020 to investigate the dynamics in the performance of the Chinese universities in this ranking scheme.

Method

The research relied on secondary data from the ARWU website. The rankings of the C9 league universities and other top performing Chinese universities from the year 2016 to 2020 was recorded and analyzed.

Table 1: ARWU global rankings for C9 league universities from 2016-2020

Institution	Yearly Rankings				
	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Shanghai Jiaotong University	101-150	101-150	101-150	82	63
University of Science and Technology, China	101-150	101-150	101-150	101-150	73
Nanjing University	201-300	201-300	151-200	151-200	101-150
Fudan University	101-150	101-150	101-150	101-150	100
Peking University	71	71	57	53	49
Xian Jiaotong University	151-200	201-300	151-200	151-200	101-150
Tsinghua University	58	48	45	43	29
Harbin	151-200	151-200	151-200	151-200	101-150

Institute of Technology					
Zhejiang University	101-150	101-150	67	70	58

Source: <http://www.shanghairanking.com/>

Table 2: ARWU global rankings for Chinese universities that have same or better ranking than some of the C9 League Universities from 2016-2020

Institution	Yearly Rankings				
	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Sun Yat-sen University	151-200	151-200	101-150	101-150	101-150
Beijing Normal University	201-300	201-300	-	-	-
Huanzhong University of Science and technology	201-300	201-300	151-200	101-150	101-150
Jilin University	201-300	-	-	-	-
Sichuan University	-	151-200	151-200	151-200	-
Central South University	-	201-300	-	151-200	101-150
South East University	-	201-300	-	151-200	101-150
Soochow University (China)	-	201-300	-	151-200	-
University of electronic science and	-	201-300	-	151-200	-

technology, of China					
Wuhan University	-	201-300	-	151-200	-

Source: <http://www.shanghairanking.com/>

Key: (-) means the institutions have not outperformed any C9 league in that particular year.

Discussion

The tables above show the positions of the C9 league and other better performing universities from 2016 to 2020 based on the ARWU scheme. Critically observing the performance of the universities on year-to-year basis, there has been a good performance generally by the schools between the year 2016 and the year 2020. In the year 2016, the school with the best position is Tsinghua University, which was at the 58th position in the world and the second best performing C9 university is Peking University, which found itself in the 71st position worldwide. Following in descending order are Shanghai Jiao Tong University, University of Science and Technology China, Zhejiang University and Fudan University, which all found themselves in the 101-150 position. Xi'an Jiao Tong University and Harbin Institute of Technology also found themselves in the 151-200 positions respectively. In the year 2016 the worst performing C9 university was Nanjing University. However, looking critically at the table 2, Sun Yat-sen University had a better performance ranking as compared to the worst performing C9 university, namely Nanjing university. Finally, for the year 2016, three universities which are not part of the C9 league of elite universities have equaled the performance of the worst performing C9 university in China. These schools are namely Beijing Normal University, Jilin University and Huanzhong University of Science and technology. In the year 2017, the best performing university in China based on the ARWU global ranking was Tsinghua University as in the previous year. Tsinghua University made a 10-point leap from being number 58 the previous year to the 48th position in the whole wide world. However, Peking University which had the 71st position in the year 2016, couldn't improve on its ranks. Peking University maintained its position at number 71. Following suite was Shanghai Jiaotong , Zhejiang, Fudan, University of Science and Technology of China and Nanjing which also maintained their ranking from the previous year. The only institution which made progress in the rankings in the year 2017 apart from Tsinghua University was Xian Jiaotong University. However, interestingly all the universities that couldn't make any progress on the ranking table by virtue of maintaining their rankings from the previous year of 2016, still had better rankings as compared to Xian Jiaotong University. Moving to the table 2 to assess the performance of other schools that either did better or are at par with the C9 schools, threw the spotlight on six new institutions namely Sichuan University, Central South University, South East University, Soochow University (China), University of Electronic Science and Technology, of China and Wuhan University. Judging from the points accumulated by these schools, only points to the fact that there is a positive impact on

the higher education system which was underpinned by research propelled by the projects undertaken by the government of China and also as a result of the heavy investments done by the stakeholders in Chinese higher education.

In the year 2018, Tsinghua University which was the best performing C9 league school, was ranked 45 as compared to its previous rank of 48. Peking University also moved from the 71 position to 57. Zhejiang University which was the third best performer for the year 2018, also had a ranking of 67, from 101-150 of the previous year, which makes it quite a significant jump. This was impressive because in the year 2017, Zhejiang University with other four peers namely Fudan, Shanghai Jiaotong and the University of Science and Technology of China all had the same ranking of 101-150. Also, from table the table 1, Nanjing University's ranking was 201-300; same as Xian Jiaotong in the year 2017 but in the year 2018, they both made a progress of 151-200. Looking at the table 2, in the year 2018, only three universities performed better than some of the C9 league universities. These universities are namely Sun Yat-sen University, Huanzhong University of Science and technology and Sichuan University. Sun Yat-sen was the best performing institution among them with a ranking of 101-150 whereas Huanzhong University of Science and technology and Sichuan University both had rankings of 151-200. This throws the spotlight on Sun Yat-sen as a consistent non C9 performer.

In a nut shell moving to the year 2019, Tsinghua university still continued its positive exploits on the ranking positions but not with a huge improvement gap. It moved from 45th position to 43rd position which was a steady progress. Zhejiang University fell from its 67th position to 70th. Peking University also improved from 57th position in 2018 to 53rd in 2019. Shanghai Jiaotong University also improved on its rankings from 101-150 to 83rd position in the rankings. Looking at table 2 for universities that are not C9 rated institutions but are competing vigorously in the year 2019, the numbers are impressive. There were 8 institutions that also performed impressively on the ranking scheme which is a good sign for higher education in China. Finally, in the year 2020, there was a collective improvement in the ranks of all the C9 league universities from the previous year. Starting with the best performing institution from last year which was Tsinghua to the worst performers; Xian Jiaotong University, Harbin Institute of Technology and Nanjing University. They all made significant gains on the ranking scale. Also in the year 2020, some of the universities that are not elitist institutions or are not C9 classified, but consistently compete with the top-tier universities in China, have also outperformed some of the C9 schools. Notable among them is Sun Yat-sen University, Huanzhong University of Science and technology, Central South University and South East University. In the year 2020, position of Tsinghua University improved from 43rd position to 29th position which was ground breaking. Peking also made a fairly significant gain from 53rd position to 49th position. Shanghai Jiaotong University rose from its 82nd positioning in the previous year to 63rd position. University of Science and Technology, China moved from 101-150 to 73rd position on the ranking scale. In the case of Fudan University, there was a significant leap from its 101-150 position from the year 2019 to 100th position in the year 2020. Xian Jiaotong

University and Harbin Institute of Technology have all made significant improvements in a similar fashion. These two universities had the same ranking of 151-200 in the previous year. Interestingly, they collectively improved on their positioning in the ranking for the year 2020, which saw them both improving to the 101-150 position on the global ranking. This points to the fact that the higher education system in china is gaining grounds internationally. Whiles China as a country is gaining influence and power in the 21st century, it's also making gains on the front of human resource development which is clearly manifested in the steady rise of its universities on the world stage.

Conclusion

The higher education reforms policies carried out by the stakeholders in China's higher educational sub-sector have been overwhelming. The formulation and implementation of projects to make Chinese higher education world-class, was a goal set by the the policy makers right from the early 1990s. The amount of time and resources injected form of investment in the higher education sector of China has yielded enormous fruits. All results with regards to the performance of the top-tier schools in China which benefit exclusively from special resources from the the Chinese government is a clear manifestation of realizing the dream of modernizing Chinese higher education. Interestingly, there are some unsung heroes (universities) that are making waves gradually on the world stage. China's higher education reforms have made higher education in China attractive and something worth looking at. However, the discovery of schools that consistently outperformed some of the C9 league schools needs to be studied. The need for investigation into factors that accounted for the excellent performance of these apparently unknown schools needs to be looked at again in the future and attention must be paid to these institutions in order to study their modes of operation and organizational structure as compared to the traditional top-tier schools. In addition, the listed C9 league of institutions with inconsistent performances on the ranking scales should be studied to know their challenges. Finally, the Chinese government should consider other new policies for its higher education network structure with substantial investment and also introduction of new members into the elitists league of universities, to encourage healthy competition among higher education institutions in order to make the lesser known but equally good performing institutions of higher learning visible on the world stage as this will go a long way to increase the number of Chinese higher education institutions in the community of first class universities in the world.

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Spencer Amoo-Dotse, College of Education, Huzhou University, Huzhou, Zhejiang, China.

Mail: desiadenyozikpitor@gmail.com

LinkedIn: [linkedin.com/in/spencer-amoo-dotse-5557a3ab](https://www.linkedin.com/in/spencer-amoo-dotse-5557a3ab)

+86 13122005620/+233200245623

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